

ATRIUM – Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities

Work Package WP7
Fostering Cross-Disciplinary Research through
Training and Open Science

Deliverable D7.1
The ATRIUM Skillset assessment and Gap Analysis report

Funding Instrument:	EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA) REA.C-Future Society.
Call:	HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01
Call Topic:	C.4 – Reforming European R&I and Research Infrastructures
Project Start:	1 Jan 2024
Project Duration:	48 months
Beneficiary in Charge:	OPERAS
Document Identifier:	10.5281/zenodo.16918112

**Funded by
the European Union**

Deliverable Information

Action Number:	101132163
Action Acronym:	ATRIUM
Action title:	Advancing FronTier Research In the Arts and hUMANities
Deliverable Number:	D7.1
Deliverable Full Title:	The ATRIUM Skillset assessment and Gap Analysis report
Beneficiary in Charge:	OPERAS
Report Version:	v1.0
Contractual Date:	31/08/2025
Report Submission Date:	21/08/2025
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Report
Lead Author(s):	Carol Delmazo (OPERAS), Iulianna van der Lek (CLARIN), Anastasia Gasia (AUEB), Sarah Bénérière (INRIA), Maria Ilvanidou (AUEB)
Co-author(s):	Sy Holsinger (OPERAS), Canan Arikan-Caba (OEAW), Vera Maria Charvát (OEAW)
Keywords:	ATRIUM project, curriculum, Digital Humanities, digital tools, FAIR, Open Science, researchers, research Infrastructures, services, skills, survey, training
Status:	Submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes
02/07/25	v0.1	Carol Delmazo, Iulianna van der Lek, Anastasia Gasia, Sarah Bénière, Maria Ilvanidou, Sy Holsinger, Vera Maria Charvát, Canan Arikan-Caba	Draft Report
23/07/25	v0.2	Françoise Gouzi, Vicky Garnett	WP7 reviewers
14/08/25	v0.3	Claudio Prandoni, Matej Ďurčo	External reviewers
20/08/25	v0.4	Carol Delmazo, Sarah Bénière, Anastasia Gasia, Iulianna van der Lek, Vera Maria Charvát, Megan Black	Final revision
21/08/25	v1.0	Carol Delmazo, Megan Black	Approved version

Table of Contents

ATRIUM – Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities	1
Deliverable Information	2
List of Tables	5
List of Figures	6
List of Abbreviations/Acronyms	7
Executive Summary	10
1. Introduction	12
1.1 Context and Scope of the Document	12
1.2 Structure of the Document	13
2. Timeline and Methodology	14
2.1 Methodology for the Questionnaire for Service Providers	14
2.2 Methodology for the Researchers’ Survey	15
3. Results	18
3.1 Questionnaire for Service Providers	18
3.1.1 Disciplines & Target Audiences	18

Disciplines	18
Target audiences	19
3.1.2 Skills Required for the Active Use of the ATRIUM Services	20
3.1.3 Gaps	28
Training Gaps	28
Access Gaps	30
3.1.4 Accessibility Issues	32
3.1.5 Service improvement and the ATRIUM Bridge	34
3.2 Researchers' Survey - Overall results	35
3.2.1 Demographics and Background	35
3.2.2 Research Activities	38
3.2.3 Open Science and FAIR	38
3.2.4 Current Skills Analysis	40
Digital Tools	40
Specific skills - ATRIUM Services	43
Standards	44
Coding/Programming	46
3.2.5 Training Needs	47
Perceived training needs	47
Challenges	50
Other inputs	51
3.3 Researchers' Survey - Cross Analysis	52
Skills Missing per Community Group	52
Training Needs per Community Group	52
4. Recommendations for the ATRIUM Curriculum	54
4.1 Training Platforms' Structure	55
Implement Personalised Learning Paths	55
Show progression	55
Implement robust filtering	55
Badging and Recognition System	56
Regular quality evaluation of resources / Feedback mechanism	56
4.2 Training Formats	56
Use video tutorials with related exercises	56
Incorporate concise chapter abstracts in written manuals/guidelines	57
Implement blended learning options	57
Create training for different proficiency levels	57
Opt for shorter modules with clear learning outcomes	57
4.3 Training Topics	57
4.3.1 Open Science and FAIR Training	58
Fundamentals of Open Science (OS) and FAIR Principles	58

Practical Application of FAIR Data Principles in Research	58
Train-the-Trainer course on Open Science and FAIR Principles	58
4.3.2 Upskilling for the use of the ATRIUM Services	59
4.3.3 Training Needs as Perceived by Researchers	59
Data Collection, Preparation, Analysis, and Visualisation	60
Data Sharing	61
Workflows	61
Knowledge Representation	61
4.3.4 Specific Training for the ATRIUM Service Providers	61
Accessibility Fundamentals for Digital Services (Focus on WCAG Basics)	61
Multilingual Access and Inclusive Documentation Practices	62
Minimising technical barriers: navigating institutional access	62
5. Conclusion	63
Beyond the ATRIUM Curriculum	64
Annex A	66
Annex B	66
Consortium	67
Research Infrastructures	67
Beneficiaries	67
Affiliated Entities	68
Disclaimer	68

List of Tables

Table 1: Work timeline

Table 2: Skills required for the active use of the ATRIUM services/software

Table 3: Proposed Topics for the ATRIUM Curriculum

List of Figures

- Figure 1: Types of audiences targeted by the ATRIUM services/software
- Figure 2: Skills categories for the active use of the ATRIUM services/software
- Figure 3: Adherence levels to accessibility guidelines of the ATRIUM services/software
- Figure 4: Countries where the survey respondents are based
- Figure 5: Use of one or multiple working languages by the survey respondents
- Figure 6: Scientific domains of the survey respondents
- Figure 7: Community groups of the survey respondents
- Figure 8: Research activities in which the survey respondents are engaged
- Figure 9: Familiarity of survey respondents with the principles and practices of Open Science
- Figure 10: Application of FAIR data principles in survey respondents' research
- Figure 11: Responses for the open-ended question 4.1. What digital tools or services do you use in your research activities? (N=276)
- Figure 12: Digital tools or services used for research activities grouped in broader categories
- Figure 13: Global overview of the respondents' level of familiarity with each skill/knowledge needed for the use of the ATRIUM services in relation to one another
- Figure 14: Standards, controlled vocabularies and thesauri that the survey participants apply in their research
- Figure 15: Programming language(s) with which the survey participants work
- Figure 16: Top 10 Researchers' Training Needs
- Figure 17: Challenges faced by researchers when using online learning resources
- Figure 18: Top 10 Training Needs per Community Group

List of Abbreviations/Acronyms

AAT	(Getty) Arts & Architecture Thesaurus
AHSS	Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMCR Digital Archive	Digital Archive of the Archaeological Map of the Czech Republic
API	Application Programming Interface
ARCHE	A Resource Centre for the HumanitiEs
ATR	Automatic Text Recognition
ATRIUM	Advancing fronTier Research In the arts and hUMANities
AUEB	Athens University of Economics and Business
BARTOC	Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies and Classifications
BCDH	Belgrade Centre for Digital Humanities
CIDOC-CRM	International Committee for Documentation Conceptual Reference Model
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CLST	Centre for Language and Speech Technology
CMDI	Component MetaData Infrastructure
CRedit	Contributor Roles Taxonomy
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DoA	Description of Action
EAD	Encoded Archival Description
EDC	European Digital Credentials
EGC	Educational Greek Corpus
EpHEMERA	Endangered architectural and archaeological Heritage in the South Eastern MEditerRAnean Area
EU	European Union

EuroSciVoc	European Science Vocabulary
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FBC	Digital Libraries Federation - Federacją Bibliotek Cyfrowych
FitSM	Free, Lightweight, IT Service Management Standard
GIS	Geographic Information System
GROBID	GeneRation Of Bibliographic Data
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HTR	Handwritten Text Recognition
HTTPS	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
INRIA	Institut National de Recherche en Informatique et en Automatique
ISAD(G)	General International Standard Archival Description
LLM	Large Language Model
LOD	Linked Open Data
MARC	MACHINE-Readable Cataloging
MD	MarkDown
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
OEAW	Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften
OPERAS	Open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities
OS	Open Science
OSCARS	Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PDF	Portable Document Format
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy

RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST (API)	REpresentational State Transfer
RI	Research Infrastructure
RiC	Records in Contexts
Skills4EOSC	Skills for the European Open Science Commons
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
TaDiRAH	Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities
TGN	(Getty) Thesaurus of Geographic Names
TNA	TransNational Access
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package
WSJP	Wielki Słownik Języka Polskiego / Great Dictionary of the Polish Language
XSLT	eXtensible Stylesheet Language Transformations

Executive Summary

The ATRIUM Skillset assessment and Gap Analysis report (Deliverable D7.1) aimed to identify and understand the existing and missing **skills** among researchers in the Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences (AHSS). It focused particularly on the skills needed for the effective use of the services available in the ATRIUM Service & Software Catalogue.¹ Another core objective was to pinpoint researchers' unmet **training needs** and the **challenges** they face when accessing online **learning resources**. The comprehensive insights, derived from a twofold analysis based on a **Questionnaire for Service Providers** and a **Researchers' Survey**, are crucial for directly informing and shaping the **ATRIUM Curriculum** that will be developed under Task 7.3.

Key findings

Questionnaire for Service Providers: assesses the target audience, required skills, training resources, and potential barriers to the adoption of ATRIUM services.

- **Audience:** The most frequent target audiences for ATRIUM services are "Researchers" (41 out of 45 services) and "Students" (30).
- **Skills:** While many ATRIUM services only require basic technical skills and domain knowledge to navigate the user interfaces and main functionalities, about 15 services demand more specialised skills, such as,
 - **Automatic Text Recognition (ATR)** skills (e.g., Handwritten Text Recognition, Optical Character Recognition).
 - **Programming Languages** (e.g., Python, Java, JavaScript, R).
 - **Backend Web Services** (e.g., REST API, HTTPS Protocol).
 - **Computer Skills** (e.g., using command line, Docker).
 - Familiarity with **GitHub** for active use, feedback, or assistance.
- **Training:** Although 34 of the services offer training, 39 have resources available only in English, indicating a significant language barrier for broader audiences.
- **Access Gaps:** Identified barriers include technical requirements (e.g., needing GPUs, specific browsers, institutional logins), language and outreach limitations, among others.
- **Accessibility Issues:** Responses revealed that the majority of services are only partially compliant with accessibility guidelines (like WCAG), highlighting a major area for improvement.

Researchers' Survey: assesses researchers' current and missing skills, identifies unmet training needs and challenges in accessing online learning resources.

- **Demographics and Background:** Most respondents are based in European countries (327 out of 334 responses), are multilingual (60.5%), work in the Humanities (71.3%), and identify as senior researchers (33.5%).

¹ <https://atrium-research.eu/services/>

- **Open Science (OS) and FAIR Principles:** Nearly half of respondents (51.2%) are familiar with the principles, with most still exploring ways to apply or only apply to some extent OS practices (79.3%) and FAIR Principles- Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (72.2%).
- **Skills for the ATRIUM Services:** A considerable proportion of researchers are "not familiar" with skills like using container management tools (79.3%), Web APIs (50.6%), coding/programming (49.1%), and command-line interfaces (44.3%).
- **Perceived Training Needs:** The top 10 categories of skills that researchers wish to acquire through online learning resources are:
 - **Data Analysis** (39.22%)
 - **Data Visualisation** (35.33%)
 - **(Automatic) Text Recognition** (23.05%)
 - **FAIR Data Principles** (19.46%)
 - **Data Publication** (18.26%)
 - **Workflows** (17.96%)
 - **Open Science** (17.37%)
 - **Programming & Development** (10.18%)
 - **AI & Machine Learning** (5.69%)
 - **Data Management** (4.19%)
- **Challenges in Online Learning:** Key challenges include finding relevant resources (Access and Availability, 35.0%), concerns about the Quality and Credibility of resources (33.8%), Time Management and Scheduling (25.4%), and issues with Certification/Recognition (14.7%).

Based on the insights gathered, the report provides recommendations for developing an inclusive and robust ATRIUM Curriculum. There are three groups of recommendations: **Training Platforms' Structure, Training Formats** and **Training Topics** (related to Open Science and FAIR Training, Upskilling for ATRIUM Services, Training Needs as Perceived by Researchers, Specific Training for ATRIUM Service Providers).

The report concludes that these insights are crucial for creating a curriculum that responds to genuine community needs. They also hold value for other research infrastructures and training providers seeking to enhance digital competencies in the AHSS landscape.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context and Scope of the Document

Digitally enabled, data-driven research is reshaping the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences (AHSS), offering unprecedented opportunities to process, analyse, and reuse data across languages, domains, and media. Yet, researchers in these fields still face substantial challenges in accessing, understanding, and using the diverse tools and services available to them. These barriers are not only technical but also relate to prior knowledge, required skills, and difficulties in engaging with unfamiliar standards and digital vocabularies.

By identifying these obstacles, the ATRIUM project aims to bridge the gap between state-of-the-art infrastructure services and the everyday needs of researchers through a robust training programme. This programme will be articulated through a pedagogical narrative in the ATRIUM Curriculum, whose guidelines and underlying principles have already been published.² The ATRIUM Curriculum will be hosted on DARIAH-Campus³, a discovery framework and hosting platform for learning resources.

A highly skilled and engaged user base is critical to the sustainability and impact of Research Infrastructures (RIs). ATRIUM brings together four leading European RIs—DARIAH, ARIADNE, CLARIN and OPERAS. Dozens of services offered by these RIs are listed in the ATRIUM Service & Software Catalogue⁴, supporting all stages of digitally enabled, data-driven research: creating, processing, analysing, preserving, and reusing digital data across a wide range of AHSS disciplines.

To ensure improved access and meaningful use of this rich catalogue, it was first necessary to better understand its intended audiences, the skills required for effective use, the availability of relevant training materials, and the potential barriers to adoption. To that end, a Questionnaire for Service Providers was developed and analysed as an initial step.

Based on the identified skill requirements for using ATRIUM services, a Researchers' Survey was designed to understand which of these skills researchers already possess, where gaps remain, and to gather direct feedback on unmet training needs and challenges in accessing online learning resources. The insights drawn from these two sources – the Questionnaire for Service Providers and the Researchers' Survey – form the basis of this Skillset Assessment and Gap Analysis report. It concludes with a set of recommendations for the ATRIUM Curriculum,

² Tasovac, T., & Garnett, V. (2024). The Guidelines for Producing the ATRIUM Curriculum. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13867113>

³ <https://campus.dariah.eu/>

⁴ <https://atrium-research.eu/services/>

ensuring that it responds to real community needs, not only to foster more effective use of ATRIUM services, but also to support a broader understanding of training needs, tool usage, and the challenges faced in digital learning across the AHSS landscape.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows:

- [Section 2](#) describes the methodology used to design, launch, and analyse both the Questionnaire for Service Providers and the Researchers' Survey.
- [Section 3](#) provides a detailed description and analysis of the results from both instruments.
- [Section 4](#) presents the recommendations for the ATRIUM Curriculum, including suggestions for training formats and topics.
- [Section 5](#) concludes the deliverable.

Finally, additional information is provided in [Annex A](#) – Instrument for the Questionnaire for Service Providers and [Annex B](#) – Instrument for the Researchers' Survey.

2. Timeline and Methodology

Both the questionnaire and the survey were designed, launched, and analysed under Task 7.1 of the ATRIUM project, titled “The ATRIUM Skillset Assessment.” This task is led by OPERAS, with contributions from the following partners: DARIAH, CLARIN, AUEB, INRIA, OEAW, and BCDH.

To ensure the results could be analysed in time for this report, the following timeline was established and followed:

Table 1: Work timeline

Mar 2024	Identification of contact points for all services listed at the time in the ATRIUM Catalogue.
Apr 2024	Design of the Questionnaire for Service Providers , including internal testing before launch.
May - Jun 2024	Distribution of the questionnaire to service providers’ contact points, with reminders sent as needed.
Jul 2024	Initial analysis of the questionnaire to support Task 7.3 in preparing the Guidelines for the ATRIUM Curriculum (Deliverable D7.2), and to inform the design of the Researchers’ Survey.
Aug - Oct 2024	Design the Researchers’ Survey .
Oct - Dec 2024	Launch and dissemination of the Researchers’ Survey across multiple channels, followed by weekly dissemination cycles. In parallel, further analysis of the questionnaire results.
Jan - May 2025	Analysis of the Researchers’ Survey.
May - Jun 2025	Development of recommendations for the ATRIUM Curriculum, based on the combined results of the Questionnaire and the Survey.

The following two subsections describe the specific methodologies used for both the Questionnaire for Service Providers and the Researchers’ Survey.

2.1 Methodology for the Questionnaire for Service Providers

The Questionnaire for Service Providers was designed using a combination of exploratory and qualitative survey methods. The exploratory approach was considered suitable, given the diversity of the ATRIUM services, allowing us to gain initial insights on skills, training, and barriers without predetermining categories or limiting responses.

While the questionnaire predominantly featured open-ended questions—encouraging service providers to describe their services, required skills, perceived barriers, and training materials in their own terms— it also included a number of closed-ended questions to capture structured information on aspects such as target audiences, disciplinary focus, feedback mechanisms, and user support strategies. You can read the full questionnaire in [Annex A](#).

Allowing respondents to frame their input freely, however, presented the task team with a significant analytical challenge. The variety of responses, while valuable for capturing nuanced perspectives, required a more time-consuming and interpretative approach to identify common themes and categories. Unlike structured, closed-ended data that can be readily quantified, the open-ended answers demanded careful reading and synthesis to extract meaningful conclusions, adding considerable complexity to the analysis phase. Consequently, a more pragmatic approach guided the Researchers' Survey design, with open-ended questions used strategically only in instances where they were expected to provide particularly valuable results.

The questionnaire responses were reviewed manually and analysed thematically using Google Sheets. The goal was to identify patterns, recurring concepts, and relevant distinctions among the services. Similar responses were grouped into broader analytical categories, such as required skills, levels of accessibility compliance, types of barriers, and available training. This enabled a more structured interpretation of the qualitative input, facilitating the identification of shared needs and challenges across services. In addition to the questionnaire responses, desk research was conducted to verify and complement the information provided.

2.2 Methodology for the Researchers' Survey

For the Researchers' Survey, a snowball sampling method was employed to reach a diverse range of researchers from Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences who use or could potentially benefit from the ATRIUM services. Initial participants – researchers connected to the ATRIUM partners – were reached through mailing lists of the ATRIUM project and its collaborating infrastructures (DARIAH, ARIADNE, CLARIN, and OPERAS). To maximise the response rate, the participants were also asked to spread the word and recruit additional potential participants from their networks who met the criteria (researchers from AHSS). In addition, the survey was disseminated through various communication channels, including the websites, social media networks and newsletters of ATRIUM and its partners. In close collaboration with the ATRIUM Communications team (WP2), the dissemination was repeated in weekly cycles from the launch (24 October 2020) to the end of 2024.

Regarding the survey design, it began with a Demographics and Background section. Recognising the importance of data privacy, we aimed to collect only the minimal personal information necessary. However, this section was crucial for understanding the geographical distribution of respondents (the countries in which they are based), their primary working languages, the community groups they identify with, and their scientific domain. This

information allowed us to contextualise the subsequent responses and tailor our understanding of their training needs.

The next section delved into the types of data researchers work with and their various research activities. We also included a dedicated section (3) on their knowledge and application of Open Science and FAIR Principles, as these are central subjects in the ATRIUM project. Section 4, titled “Skills for the use of research services and tools”, directly addressed whether researchers had the knowledge and skills previously identified in the questionnaire as necessary for effectively using the ATRIUM services. For sections 3 and 4, we mainly offered a straightforward set of three responses in closed-ended questions. Participants could indicate their familiarity or experience with a concept or tool by selecting one of the following options: no familiarity, some familiarity or experience, or high familiarity. The final section of the questionnaire aimed to gather insights about the researchers’ perceived training needs and skills gaps, their preferred training formats, and the type of challenges they encountered when using online training resources. The full instrument is in [Annex B](#).

As explained above, we strategically limited the use of open-ended questions in the Researchers' Survey, reserving them for areas where we anticipated gaining richer and more nuanced insights. This approach proved valuable, particularly in uncovering a wider array of tools currently used by researchers, as well as providing an in-depth understanding of their specific training needs and the obstacles they face in online learning. This qualitative data supplemented the structured responses, offering valuable context and guiding our understanding of the researchers' perspectives.

The analysis of the Researchers’ Survey combined both quantitative and qualitative methods. The structured questions allowed for quantitative summarisation, while the open-ended responses provided richer insights that supported more nuanced interpretation. Qualitative data collected through open-ended questions were cleaned, normalised, and categorised to reduce ambiguity and enable systematic analysis. This was primarily accomplished using OpenRefine⁵, an open-source data transformation tool, which facilitated the grouping of free-text responses into broader conceptual categories.

Quantitative data from the closed questions and the categorised qualitative responses were analysed using Google Sheets. Pivot tables and frequency counts enabled the detection of patterns and facilitated cross-analysis. Cross-tabulation techniques were employed to examine the interconnections between the skills needed for the ATRIUM services and those missing in each community group. Additionally, recurring training needs and gaps across specific user groups were also examined.

Specific decisions were made during the analysis process to ensure clarity and consistency, particularly regarding visualisation tools to accurately reflect the results (e.g., avoiding pie charts for questions that allow multiple answers). In addition, in the categorisation of

⁵ <https://openrefine.org/>

open-ended questions, whenever respondents were asked to provide specific information (e.g. naming the standards they use or describing challenges they face when using online training resources), generic or non-substantive responses such as “none,” “all,” “I don’t know,” or similar were grouped under a general category labeled “N/A” or “No specific needs” in each analysis.

In the data cleaning and normalisation process, particular attention was paid to defining what constituted a unique value. Similar or overlapping entries were merged into broader categories to avoid fragmentation and improve interpretability. These decisions were guided by both frequency of occurrence and semantic proximity, ensuring that the grouped data still accurately reflected the respondents’ inputs while remaining analytically useful.

The mixed-methods approach also allowed for the triangulation of findings, where structured responses and qualitative insights could be interpreted side by side. This helped to contextualise individual responses within broader trends and inform evidence-based recommendations for the ATRIUM Curriculum. Overall, the methodological approach ensured that both the diversity of digital practices, the varying levels of expertise and the diverse training needs and challenges among respondents were adequately captured and analysed.

3. Results

3.1 Questionnaire for Service Providers

The questionnaire was distributed via email between April and June 2024 to the identified contact points of the providers whose services and software were listed in the ATRIUM portfolio⁶, as originally written in the project description. The updated list of services was later publicly available as the ATRIUM Service & Software Catalogue.⁷ It is a diverse set of services designed to support different stages of data-driven research activities in the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences. Since the skills needed for their active use vary, this questionnaire was necessary at the beginning of Task 7.1.

By the time the questionnaire was conducted, the project had listed 47 services and software.⁸ If a provider offered more than one service/tool, the contact point was asked to complete a separate form for each. This resulted in data being collected on 45 of the 47 services. The following subsections detail the information gathered about their intended audiences, the skills required to use these services, the availability of training materials and potential barriers that may prevent users from accessing them.

3.1.1 Disciplines & Target Audiences

Disciplines

The questionnaire targeted services from the following disciplines:

- Social Sciences disciplines
- Humanities disciplines
- Arts disciplines
- Specific for archaeology
- Others: _____

Since one of the core RIs within ATRIUM is focused on Archaeology (ARIADNE), it was important to assess the services designed only for this discipline, which is the case of six of them (AMCR Digital Archive, ARIADNE Data Management Plan, ARIADNE EpHEMERA, ARIADNE portal,

⁶ Service portfolio: Internal list that details all the services offered by a service provider, including those in preparation, live and discontinued ([FitSM-0 V3](#))

⁷ Service catalogue: Customer-facing list of all live services offered along with relevant information about these services ([FitSM-0 V3](#))

⁸ This list has evolved as the project developed. The updated catalogue is available here: <https://atrium-research.eu/services/>

Dendrochronology Entity Recognizer, Multilingual NLP Archaeological Reports Ariadne Infrastructure). The majority of the services (27) are designed for researchers in the Social Sciences and/or Humanities (including Archaeology) and/or Arts, which are the domains targeted by DARIAH and OPERAS, the other two core RIs in ATRIUM. As CLARIN – the fourth core ATRIUM RI – is focused on language resources, its services also target the needs of the Social Sciences and Humanities disciplines. Twelve services are not (or relatively not) discipline-specific and can be used in other fields, respecting their specific purpose. For example, the Virtual Transcription Laboratory can be used by researchers in any discipline as long as their goal is to create transcriptions/annotations.

Target audiences

The “Intended Audience” controlled vocabulary⁹, as used in the SSH Open Marketplace¹⁰, was the reference to create the answers regarding target audiences in the questionnaire. The option 'publishers' was added, since this is a relevant audience for some of the services and it was absent in the April 2024 version of this controlled vocabulary. The option “other” was also made available. Figure 1 below presents the types of audiences targeted by ATRIUM services and tools.

ATRIUM Services/Tools vs Targeted Audiences

Figure 1: Types of audiences targeted by the ATRIUM services/software

The audience most frequently mentioned was “Researchers” (41 out of 45 services/software), followed by “Students” (30). These two audiences should be prioritised when designing the

⁹ <https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshoc-audience/en/>

¹⁰ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/>

ATRIUM Curriculum. “Citizen scientists” and “Public” were mentioned by nearly half of the respondents, and may indicate a need to have learning content in the curriculum open to a broader audience.

The results of this analysis were used to improve the information about the services both in their description in the ATRIUM Service & Software Catalogue and their entries in the SSH Open Marketplace, which provide detailed information about each one, including the disciplines and the target audiences.¹¹

3.1.2 Skills Required for the Active Use of the ATRIUM Services

The analysis of the skills required to actively use the software or services was primarily based on responses to open-ended question 8¹², regarding previous knowledge and/or practical skills required for the active use of the service/software. Additional insights were drawn from responses to question 13¹³, which asked about potential gaps or limitations in the use of the service/software. Some providers also used question 13 to highlight necessary skills or knowledge, so this information was integrated into this analysis.

The goal was to systematise the responses and create categories based on the skills referenced by the providers. Some skills listed were sometimes mentioned as optional and/or depended on the tasks the user wished to perform. Indeed, for many services, “working with web applications” actually means navigating the application and/or a basic usage of the service (see figure 2). For example, simply using GROBID does not require skills in Java programming; however, developing a GROBID module for a specific project would require skills in Java programming.

¹¹ The full list of tools and services of the ATRIUM Catalogue on the SSH Open Marketplace can be explored by entering the keyword “ATRIUM Catalogue” into the search box on the homepage. This search will direct you to the complete list of tools and services, as well as workflows created using them. Alternatively, when clicking on the service’s name in the ATRIUM Catalogue, after the descriptions there is a “more info” button that directs the reader to the service’s entry in the SSH Open Marketplace.

¹² Questionnaire for Service Providers - Question 8: Which previous knowledge (theoretical background) and/or practical skills (e.g. the use of GitHub, basic NLP skills) are required for the active use of the service/software? In case of software, what are the steps needed to run it? (download, local installation)

¹³ Questionnaire for Service Providers - Question 13: Are you aware of any access gap or restrictions in the use of the service/software?

8. Which previous knowledge and/or practical skills are required for the active use of the service/software?

Figure 2: Skills categories for the active use of the ATRIUM services/software

As a result, the skills were grouped into nine broader skills: [1] Knowledge/Understanding of Concepts, [2] Navigating the Service's Website/Application, [3] Automatic Text Recognition, [4] Information Extraction, [5] Data Visualisation, [6] Programming Languages, [7] Backend Web Services, [8] Computer Skills and [9] Github.

Knowledge/Understanding of Concepts

This category emphasises the importance of understanding key concepts, including Open Science, FAIR Principles, metadata, standards (such as CIDOC-CRM and ARIADNE Ontology), licenses (e.g., Creative Commons), the Semantic Web, Linked Open Data, and data management. This category refers to 9 services (see Table 2 below).

Navigating the Service's Website/Application

Thirty services require the user to know how to navigate the interface in order to use the service.¹⁴ In this case, skills like heavy programming or working with a REST API are not necessary. This is regardless of the users' knowledge of their own data and their comprehension of the underlying concepts that the users are expected to understand.

Automatic Text Recognition

¹⁴ 14 out of 30 responses informed that no specific skills were required for the active use of the service. We counted them in the "Navigating the Service's Website/Application" because it meant that the service was available through a website and simply required the user to browse it for using it. Others suggested several ways of using their service, among which browsing a website or application for performing their tasks.

Three services require skills and knowledge about Automatic Text Recognition (ATR), which encompasses both Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) and Optical Character Recognition (OCR).

Information Extraction

NLP tasks, such as Named Entity Recognition, were grouped under the “Information Extraction” category. When mentioned, “NLP skills” can either refer to [1] a knowledge of basic NLP concepts, [2] the usage of a specific tool developed for NLP tasks, or [3] the usage of the spaCy Python library. Seven services are under this category.

Data Visualisation

The only service mentioning data visualisation skills is 3DHOP.

Programming Languages

Programming languages were listed as skills, regardless of their proficiency level. The importance of understanding and mastering one of the listed programming languages depends on the expected usage of the service. In most cases, however, the programming languages mentioned are relevant primarily for technical or development tasks (e.g. creating new modules or improving the software) rather than for typical use by researchers.

- C++: NameTag, NEXUS, UDPipe
- HTML: 3DHOP,
- Java: GROBID, GATE¹⁵
- JavaScript: 3DHOP, Annotorius, NEXUS, OpenLIME (library),
- Python: ARIADNE Lab VRE, Dendrochronology Entity Recognizer, GROBID, OPERAS Metrics, NameTag, Research Spotlight, UDPipe
- R: ARIADNE Lab VRE

Backend Web Services

Ten services listed skills in backend web services like REST APIs and HTTPS Protocol. As mentioned in the previous subsection on programming languages, such skills rather come under engineering tasks that would not be performed by a researcher using the service solely for research purposes.

Computer Skills

Essential computer skills are common to many services, such as using the command line and Docker. Indeed, several services are launched via a command run in the terminal, or via the Docker platform:

- Command line: NameTag, Tesseract, X3ML Engine
- Docker: eScriptorium, GATE, OPERAS Metrics

¹⁵ Knowledge of Java and Python are required to use the GATE NLP tools. GROBID requires knowledge of Java for developers willing to develop their own modules.

- Both: GROBID, OCR4All

GitHub

Five services explicitly mentioned GitHub for their active use, as shown in Table 2 below. However, some services use GitHub issues also to gather feedback from users (22 services) and to provide assistance to them (21).

You can see a summary of the skills required for the active use of the ATRIUM services/software in the table below. This analysis served as the basis for designing Section 4: “Skills for the use of research services and tools” of the Researchers’ Survey, where we placed specific questions to assess whether researchers possess the above-described skills needed for the active use of ATRIUM services.

Table 2: Skills required for the active use of the ATRIUM services/software

Service	Knowledge / Understanding of Concepts	Navigating the Service's Website / Application	Automatic Text Recognition	Information Extraction	Data Visualisation	Programming Languages	Backend Web Services	Computer Skills	GitHub
3DHOP					X	X			
3M - Mapping Memory Manager		X							
AMCR Digital Archive		X							
Annotorious						X			X
ARCHE	X	X					X		
ARIADNE Data Management Plan		X							
ARIADNE EpHEMERA		X							
ARIADNE Lab VRE	X	X				X			
ARIADNE Linked Open Data	X	X							
ARIADNE Portal		X							
ARIADNE Visual Media Service		X							

Service	Knowledge / Understanding of Concepts	Navigating the Service's Website / Application	Automatic Text Recognition	Information Extraction	Data Visualisation	Programming Languages	Backend Web Services	Computer Skills	GitHub
ARIADNE Vocabulary Matching Tool	X	X							
CLST Language and Speech Tools		X		X					
DARIAH-Campus		X							
Datasheet Editor		X							
Dendrochronology Entity Recognizer				X		X	X		
Digital Repository of Scientific Institutes		X							
eScriptorium			X					X	
FBC (Digital Libraries Federation)		X							
GATE						X	X	X	
GATE Cloud							X		
GeoBrowser		X							

Service	Knowledge / Understanding of Concepts	Navigating the Service's Website / Application	Automatic Text Recognition	Information Extraction	Data Visualisation	Programming Languages	Backend Web Services	Computer Skills	GitHub
GoTriple		X							
GROBID						X		X	X
Journals of the Polish Academy of Sciences		X							
Language Resource Switchboard		X		X			X		
LINDAT Translation		X							
Multilingual NLP Archaeological Reports Ariadne Infrastructure				X					X
NameTag		X		X		X	X	X	
NEXUS						X			
OCR4all			X					X	
OpenLIME						X			
OPERAS Metrics						X		X	
Recogito		X							

Service	Knowledge / Understanding of Concepts	Navigating the Service's Website / Application	Automatic Text Recognition	Information Extraction	Data Visualisation	Programming Languages	Backend Web Services	Computer Skills	GitHub
Research Spotlight				X		X			X
SSH Open Marketplace		X							
SSH Vocabulary Commons	X	X					X		
TEITOK		X					X		
Tesseract			X					X	
Transformations: A DARIAH Journal	X	X							
UDPipe		X		X		X	X		
Virtual Language Observatory	X	X							
Virtual Transcription Laboratory		X							
Vocabs Services	X	X					X		
X3ML Engine	X							X	X

3.1.3 Gaps

Training Gaps

The questionnaire contained two open-ended questions, which aimed to gather information about the type of training the ATRIUM service providers offered to their users and whether they had specific suggestions for the ATRIUM Curriculum. The answers were analysed manually in Google Sheets and organised thematically. Additionally, desktop research was conducted to review the websites of the service providers and verify the information provided, including the types of training available, their formats, and languages.

Question 11¹⁶, “Are you providing training for this service/software?” revealed that a significant majority, 34 of the 45 services, offer training in various formats through active in-person or online training sessions, self-paced tutorials, user guides, and consultancy sessions tailored to the needs of interested stakeholders. Among those offering training, 11 services deliver training opportunities regularly, ensuring consistent support and knowledge reinforcement. Another 9 services offer training on request, allowing flexibility and catering to specific user inquiries or challenges. A smaller fraction (4) indicated that active training was offered occasionally, in response to service updates or through workshops at events and summer schools.

In terms of format, most training resources are offered in accessible formats, e.g. text, MD, PDF, HTML, and video. Eight services did not offer any active training, whereas 3 services (LINDAT, ARIADNE Data Management Plan, and ARIADNE EpHEMERA) indicated that they were self-explanatory and therefore did not require active training. Regarding available languages, 39 services have their web pages and training resources available only in English. Only eScriptorium, Recogito, and the Virtual Transcription Laboratory localised their training resources in languages other than English, aiming to reach a wider audience. Some services, such as AMCR Digital Archive, ARCHE, FBC, the Journals of the Polish Academy of Sciences, and Tesseract, have their websites and training resources available in both their national languages and English.

The answers to Question 12¹⁷, “Training topics/resources/formats useful to improve the use of the service/software and could be included in the ATRIUM Curriculum” provided suggestions for topics/resources/formats to be considered for the ATRIUM Curriculum based on the training gaps the service providers identified in their offer. Of the total number of responses, nearly half contained suggestions for the curriculum, which have been mapped against the skills categories identified in the Researchers’ Survey, see Table 3.

¹⁶ Questionnaire for Service Providers - Question 11: Are you providing training for this service/software? If yes, please describe it in as much detail as possible: type of training, materials available (if they are online), language(s)...

¹⁷ Questionnaire for Service Providers - Question 12: Are there any training topics/resources/formats that you think would be useful to improve the use of the service/software and could be included in the ATRIUM Curriculum?

Table 3: Proposed Topics for the ATRIUM Curriculum

Category	Proposed Training Topic (s)	Format	Proposed by
Open Science & FAIR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to ARIADNE Lab and how to use it for collaborative research • Data discovery in the Virtual Language Observatory • GoTriple workflow for SSH 	Hands-on case studies in real-world archaeological research projects and SSH in general	ARIADNE Lab VRE Virtual Language Observatory GoTriple
Programming & development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic command line • How to use REST web service • Basic Python • Spacy NLP • JupyterHub • RStudio • Analytics Engine 	Hands-on, in-depth training	NameTag ARIADNE Lab VRE
Data management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to structure data in a spreadsheet to make it machine-readable • Metadata creation for data providers 	Hands-on training, MOOC-like tutorial	ARCHE FBC eScriptorium
Text recognition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General introduction to OCR/HTR and OCR4ALL 	Workshop	OCR4ALL
Text processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language Resource Switchboard • Transcription portal 	Webinar	Language Resource Switchboard CLST Language and Speech Tools
Data preservation and archiving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to Archive and Reference the Software Code 	Best practice guide/workflow	SSH Open Marketplace
Knowledge representation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to create controlled vocabularies in the SSH • Introduction to LOD and the ARIADNE Ontology • How to use web GUI and SPARQL • Data modelling and ontology design • Knowledge graph creation from text 	Hands-on tutorials	Vocabs Services ARIADNE Linked Open Data Research Spotlight
Data publishing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diamond publishing model (Episciences and Transformations) 	Training resource on DARIAH-Campus	Transformations

Access Gaps

One of the purposes of the questionnaire was to identify access gaps in the use of the services: e.g. if the service/software is more accessed in some countries than in others, or accessed by some specific communities more than others, or if there are access restrictions (log in to the university account, the user interface language, etc.). Thus, service providers were asked (open-ended question 13¹⁸) if they were aware of any access gap or restrictions in the use of their services/software. We categorised the responses into four categories of barriers for the use of the services:

Technical and access barriers: the services/software require specific computing infrastructure or institutional access controls

ARIADNE Vocabulary Matching Tool

The application requires a modern web browser with JavaScript enabled to function correctly.

CLST Language and Speech Tools

The portal may give a timeout error when heavily loaded. This is intended to be addressed during the ATRIUM project to ensure its smooth operation.

eScriptorium

Realistic use of the software requires access to GPUs and relatively powerful servers. Currently, there are approximately 20 such installations, but they are either institutional or project-based, and therefore, there is no general access at the national or European level.

LINDAT Translation

By the time of the questionnaire, it supported plaintext only, but there is a plan to support many other formats (.odt, .odp, .docx, .pptx, etc.).

X3ML Engine

In most cases, it is used through 3M, which is another service listed in the ATRIUM Catalogue.

Digital Repository of Scientific Institutes

Data deposited in the repository is managed by the partners who provide the resource. Curators from a given partner (based on the type of license obtained from the author) decide how a given item will be made available. For instance, one can initially limit access to the library premises only, and then, after a specific period, make the item available in an open-access manner.

Language Resource Switchboard

While most tools and services connected to Switchboard are freely accessible, some of them (e.g. Weblicht and the CLST Automatic Speech Recognition services provided by Radboud

¹⁸ Questionnaire for Service Providers - Question 13: Are you aware of any access gap or restrictions in the use of the service/software?

University) require authentication through the CLARIN Service Provider Federation¹⁹ account, provided by many universities and institutions.

Policy-related barriers: for the use of the service/software, data should follow a specific policy

ARCHE

Recent data show that the top three countries in terms of the number of people accessing ARCHE (in this order) are Germany, Austria, and the United States. The collection policy of ARCHE requires that the data deposited have some connection to Austria; however, this criterion can still allow, for example, for data from archaeological excavations conducted by Austrian institutions abroad. Also, three levels of access restriction can be defined for resources stored in ARCHE, depending on legal requirements associated with the data; while most of them are "public" (freely accessible to anyone), some of them are "academic" (requiring a log-in with your own university's credentials) or "restricted" (requiring a special password).

Language barriers: limited knowledge of one or more languages reported as a challenge for the use of the service/software

AMCR Digital Archive

The service is mainly used by domestic users (the Czech Republic) and is not so well-known abroad. As such, most of the service is in the Czech language. This language barrier is planned to be partly overcome during the ATRIUM project.

LINDAT Translation

Providers plan to add more languages.

GATE

Documentation and support are only available in English.

ARIADNE Vocabulary Matching Tool

UI languages are (currently) limited to English, German, French, Spanish, Italian, and Dutch.

These are the access gaps reported by service providers in question 13 of the questionnaire. However, we are aware that other services and software from the catalogue offer similar barriers, namely having the user experience and documentation only in English.

Outreach limitations: services/software are used by a limited community, and can be used by a broader community

3M - Mapping Memory Manager

This service is primarily used by universities and research communities.

¹⁹ <https://www.clarin.eu/content/service-provider-federation>

TEITOK

TEITOK is primarily popular due to informal promotion, with most users coming from two research communities: diachronic Spanish corpora and the Czech repository.

Vocabs services

Although the services can be used by a wide public, in practice, they are mainly research-oriented and are mostly limited to the European (and especially the DARIAH-EU) community.

Transformations: A DARIAH Journal

Episciences is growing internationally and, through specific funding (provided by OSCARS), will be able to connect to other national repositories in Europe.

3.1.4 Accessibility Issues

The responses regarding the accessibility of tools and services provided in the ATRIUM Catalogue reveal a mixed picture of compliance with accessibility guidelines, such as Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0 and 2.1, and the efforts to accommodate users with disabilities. Since the question²⁰ about accessibility was open-ended, we categorised the responses into four (4) broader levels of adherence to accessibility guidelines: [1] strong, [2] limited, [3] planned improvements, and [4] not applicable or no answer. Additionally, the responses highlight varying levels of awareness, implementation, and prioritisation of accessibility features among the service providers.

Only seven (7) of the 45 services indicate that they actively adhere to accessibility guidelines, incorporating best practices to enhance usability for people with disabilities. These include the following features:

- Use of clear language and compatibility with assistive technologies.
- Interfaces designed with accessibility standards, such as WCAG 2.1 compliance.
- Testing of WCAG compliance.

However, even within this category, while some services demonstrate a foundational commitment to accessibility, there remains significant room for improvement.

The majority of services (20) reflect partial compliance or significant limitations in accessibility. Key challenges include:

²⁰ Questionnaire for Service Providers - Question 14: How far does the service/software adhere to guidelines that make it more accessible to a wider range of people with disabilities?

- Interfaces that pose challenges for users with specific disabilities (e.g., visual impairments).
- Services that have not fully implemented accessibility standards.
- Services that are constrained by technical complexities, such as 3D visualisations.
- No official testing of WCAG compliance.
- Instances where compliance is "basic" or marginal.
- Research infrastructures that integrate tools and services created by third parties who may not have considered accessibility issues.

This group highlights both an awareness of the importance of accessibility and the practical limitations encountered, such as the inherent constraints of the tools.

Five services describe plans for future improvements, indicating a commitment to addressing accessibility gaps. Common plans include:

- Adding features like compatible fonts and keyboard navigation.
- Updating to newer versions with full WCAG 2.1 compliance.

These responses illustrate a forward-looking approach, with teams recognising deficiencies and actively working towards better accessibility compliance.

Finally, 13 services either marked the question as not applicable or did not provide relevant feedback. These cases include:

- Software libraries or tools for developers where accessibility for end users is perceived as not relevant.
- Instances where no analysis of accessibility has been conducted.
- Ambiguity or uncertainty from respondents, such as "Don't know" or "Nothing to report."

This group suggests areas where accessibility considerations are either overlooked or deemed irrelevant to the services' scope. It also points to potential gaps in awareness or understanding of accessibility requirements.

The analysis of the results indicates that adherence to accessibility guidelines is an area where ATRIUM could offer additional training, guidance, and targeted support.

Figure 3: Adherence levels to accessibility guidelines of the ATRIUM services/software

3.1.5 Service improvement and the ATRIUM Bridge

As previously explained, the information gathered in the Questionnaire for Service Providers helped improve the services' description both in the ATRIUM Service & Software Catalogue and their entries in the SSH Open Marketplace. It served as an initial step to better understand the intended audiences, required skills, availability of training materials, and potential barriers to adoption for the diverse set of ATRIUM services.

While direct service improvement falls outside the scope of the Skillset Assessment and Gap Analysis (7.1), the results of this task directly informs and feeds into the organisation of workshop formats under Task 7.2, known as "The ATRIUM Bridge". The events are specifically designed to foster continuous service enhancement and help address the various barriers identified in the questionnaire. They include:

The ATRIUM Researcher Forum:²¹ This event convenes service providers, experts, and end-users to collect direct feedback on ATRIUM services, with the explicit aim of identifying their strengths and areas requiring improvement.

²¹ [Report of First Researcher Forum](#)

The ATRIUM Mutual Learning Exercise:²² This format brings together service and data providers. Its purpose is to gather feedback specifically from data providers to support service enhancement and contribute to the development of best practices for managing digital services within the Social Sciences and Humanities domain.

Finally, insights gained from the questionnaire have directly informed specific training recommendations tailored for service providers themselves, as explained in section 4.3.4.

3.2 Researchers' Survey - Overall results

The Questionnaire for Service Providers provided a better understanding of the ATRIUM services. The next step was to conduct a survey with researchers from the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences to capture their skills gaps and training needs. The survey was disseminated via diverse channels (social media networks, mailing lists, direct emails...) from October 24, 2024, to December 31, 2024. The results are summarised below.

3.2.1 Demographics and Background

Researchers who responded to the survey were based in 31 countries. Of the 334 responses, 327 researchers were from 26 European countries, while seven were from outside Europe, specifically Canada, the United States, Brazil, Jordan, and Kenya. Most responses came from France (76), Greece (55), Portugal (25), Austria (23) and Germany (17).

1.2. In which country are you based?

334 responses

²² [Report on the first ATRIUM Mutual Learning Exercise \(GoTriple\)](#)

Figure 4: Countries where the survey respondents are based

Most researchers consider themselves multilingual (60.5%), using two languages (38.6%), three languages (17.4%), four languages (2.7%), or five languages (1.8%). The remaining 39.5% use one working language. English prevails among 33 languages, with 68.3% of the respondents using it either alone or in combination with other languages.

Next in frequency are French (29.3%), German (17.4%) and Greek (17.4%). It is important to note that the languages cited may reflect the geographical distribution of survey participants, predominantly from specific European nations. Exceptions are Japanese (0.9%), Chinese (0.6%), Latin (0.6%), Hebrew (0.3%) and Sign Languages (0.3%), among others.

Figure 5: Use of one or multiple working languages by the survey respondents

Similarly, for the scientific domain, respondents were allowed to choose more than one option. The majority worked in one single domain (82.3%) while a smaller proportion were active across two (15.6%) or three (2.1%) domains. The Humanities domain prevails either for people who selected only this option (55.1%) or if selected in combination with other options (71.3%). Social Sciences was selected by 30.5% of respondents, either alone or in combination with other domains, followed by Other (11.4%) and Arts (6.6%). The figure below represents the total number of responses and the percentage of respondents regardless of whether the scientific domain was selected separately or in combination with other domain (s).

1.4. What is your scientific domain?

Figure 6: Scientific domains of the survey respondents

Regarding the community group, most of the respondents are Senior researchers, with 12+ years working in the field (33.5%), followed by PhD students (21.9%), Early-career researchers with up to 7 years working in the field (17.4%), Mid-career researchers, with 7-12 years working in the field (14.4%), Other (6.6%) and Masters students (6.3%).

1.6. Which community group do you identify with?

Figure 7: Community groups of the survey respondents

3.2.2 Research Activities

Respondents predominantly engage in multiple research activities. We suggested 11 activities (and "Other"), allowing them to choose multiple activities. Data analysis and data collection are the most common ones:

Figure 8: Research activities in which the survey respondents are engaged

Regarding the type of data, the respondents indicated that they work mainly with textual data (88%), images (48.2%), and tabular data (38%). The other options for types of data were: geospatial (24.9%), audio (21.3%), video (20.4%), graph (16.5%), 3D models (9.6%), and other (10.5%).

Most respondents (59.9%) reported working with both born-digital and analogue data, while 25.4% deal exclusively with analogue data, and 14.7% with born-digital data only. Among those who answered 'analogue only' or 'both' (285 respondents), 75.8% indicated they have digitised analogue data, while 24.2% have not. This suggests a potential technological gap (e.g. inability to perform digitisation).

3.2.3 Open Science and FAIR

One specific section assessed respondents' familiarity with the principles and practices of Open Science (OS) and the FAIR data principles. We also aimed to understand the extent to which they apply Open Science practices and FAIR data principles in their research. To enhance clarity, we included practical examples of applying OS practices and FAIR Principles in each response option.

Regarding Open Science principles and practices, nearly half of the respondents (51.2%) consider themselves familiar, and 44.3% are somewhat familiar. Fifteen researchers (4.5%) stated that they were not at all familiar with the concept of Open Science.

3.1. How familiar are you with the principles and practices of Open Science?

Figure 9: Familiarity of survey respondents with the principles and practices of Open Science

In terms of application of OS practices, 18% of the total number of respondents stated that they apply them extensively (e.g. conducting pre-registration, publication of methods). The majority (79.3%) chose the option "I am exploring ways to apply them in my research, or I apply them to some extent (e.g. publishing articles in Open Access, making data as open as possible)". Nine researchers (2.7%) informed us that they are not interested in applying OS practices.

More than half of respondents (51.2%) consider themselves familiar with the FAIR data principles, 30.2% are somewhat familiar, and 18.6% answered that they are not familiar with FAIR data principles.

Regarding the application of the FAIR Principles, 22.5% reported that they already apply them extensively in their research (e.g., assessing data for FAIRness before publication, creating detailed metadata using domain-specific standards, providing supporting documentation, and actively engaging with the research community to promote FAIR practices). The majority of respondents (72.2%) indicated that they are exploring ways to apply them or are already applying them to some extent (e.g., sharing data in a public repository, assigning DOIs to datasets, providing basic metadata, and using Creative Commons licenses). Eighteen researchers (5.4%) informed us they are not interested in applying FAIR data principles.

3.4. To what extent do you apply the FAIR data principles in your research?

334 responses

Figure 10: Application of FAIR data principles in survey respondents' research

This section provides essential background information on the decision to include training paths dedicated to Open Science and FAIR in the ATRIUM Curriculum. As shown in Section 3.2.5 below, many researchers also expressed a need for training in these topics: 17.37% mentioned Open Science, and 19.46% mentioned FAIR Data Principles.

3.2.4 Current Skills Analysis

Digital Tools

The survey responses to the question²³, "4.1. What digital tools or services do you use in your research activities?" reveal a diverse and extensive landscape of digital tools and services employed by researchers in the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences. As this was an optional open-ended question, 276 (82.6%) of the 334 respondents answered it, providing interesting insights. The responses were carefully cleaned, normalised, and grouped into general categories using OpenRefine. As a result, the final dataset focused on specific tools and services, excluding references to activities, programming languages, resources, standards, open repositories, or generic descriptions – topics addressed in other survey questions. The cleaned and normalised dataset comprised 366 unique tools and services cited 998 times.

Among the people who replied to this question, on average, 3.6 tools or services are mentioned per respondent, with the range spanning from 1 to 30 tools/services. This suggests that while some researchers rely on a few select tools to perform their research activities, others integrate a wide array of resources into their work. It is possible, though, that this is also related

²³ Researchers' Survey - Question 4.1: What digital tools or services do you use in your research activities? (e.g. spreadsheets, tools/services for transcription, data visualisation, translation, project management, data mapping, collaboration, etc.)

to some respondents being more meticulous than others or some tools being so deeply integrated into daily practice that respondents may overlook mentioning them (e.g., word processors). Notably, the large majority of these tools (62.6%) were mentioned only once, pointing to a highly diverse and fragmented use of tools for research. This may indicate that many niche or specialised solutions are employed by individual researchers. It may also be linked to the wide array of disciplines covered under the umbrella of the (Digital) Humanities and Social Sciences.

Figure 11: Responses for the open-ended question 4.1. What digital tools or services do you use in your research activities? (N=276)

Although each tool may serve multiple purposes and researchers often use them creatively, for the analysis the tools have been grouped into 18 broader categories, following a bottom-up approach (from tools to categories). These span a wide range of research activities, including data analysis, project management, geospatial analysis, collaboration, multimedia production, and artificial intelligence applications, among others. The top five categories, which collectively account for more than half (57.6%) of all mentions to tools and services, are: Office and Productivity (81.5%), with tools and services such as spreadsheets, Google Workspace, and Microsoft 365; Text Analysis and NLP (43.7%), with tools such as AntConc, Voyant Tools, and TXM; Programming and Development (32.2%), with tools such as Oxygen, GitHub, and pandas; AI & Machine Learning (31.1%), with tools such as ChatGPT, DeepL, and Hugging Face; and Quantitative & Statistical Analysis (19.5%), with tools such as OpenRefine, Jupyter Notebook, and RStudio being the most frequently mentioned.

What digital tools or services do you use in your research activities?

All categories ▼

Source: ATRIUM project
 Researchers Survey, 2024

Figure 12: Digital tools or services used for research activities grouped in broader categories (Explore the data at <https://public.flourish.studio/visualisation/21919068>)

Understandably, Office and Productivity is the dominant category, as these are foundational tools used across all disciplines, while they are heavily relied upon for administrative and collaborative tasks. The remaining top-five categories, however, may reveal an interesting trend toward computational and data-intensive research. Additionally, while not all text

analysis, programming or quantitative work is AI-focused, tools and services in these categories are often part of data science pipelines that feed into AI and Machine Learning, and may reflect the growing influence of the latter in AHSS research.

Among the most frequently mentioned digital tools, spreadsheets emerged as the clear leader with 47.1% of the survey participants mentioning them, underscoring their essential—and enduring—role in data organisation and analysis. In some cases, the respondents specified the exact type of spreadsheets they use, with Microsoft Excel by far the most popular (20.7%) followed by Google Sheets (5.8%) and LibreOffice Calc (1.8%). Similarly, word processors, which are the second most frequently mentioned tool (10.1%), are further specified with Microsoft Word and Google Docs being equally popular (5.1% each). Other commonly used tools or services include DeepL (9%), highlighting the importance of translation services in research workflows, QGIS (6.9%), indicating strong engagement with geospatial analysis—particularly relevant to archaeological research—, and Transkribus (6.9%), illustrating the significance of automated transcription and analysis through HTR techniques.

Specific skills - ATRIUM Services

Respondents were asked about their familiarity or experience with skills and knowledge identified as essential for using some of the ATRIUM services, including: standards; Automatic Text Recognition (ATR); and programming and development skills, such as command-line interfaces; coding/programming; encoding languages; container management tools (such as Docker/Kubernetes); GitHub/GitLab; and Web APIs.

As shown in Figure 13, many researchers lack familiarity with certain technical skills: 79.3% are not familiar with the use of container management tools and 50.6% with Web APIs. In regards to computer science-oriented skills, 49.1% are unfamiliar with coding or programming and 44.3% don't know how to use a command-line interface.

Figure 13: Global overview of the respondents' level of familiarity with each skill/knowledge needed for the use of the ATRIUM services in relation to one another

Standards

Out of 334 respondents, 225 responded either "somewhat familiar" or "familiar" to the question about their familiarity with standards, controlled vocabularies and thesauri (4.2.1).²⁴ In an open-ended question (4.2.2)²⁵, we asked these 225 respondents to specify which standards, controlled vocabularies and thesauri they usually apply in their research. Desktop research was conducted to verify the websites and other online resources that describe the specified standards. This process was quite laborious: respondents' use of abbreviations made standard identification difficult.

The responses were cleaned and normalised, resulting in 135 unique standards that were mapped into 24 types, which were further grouped into 12 categories, using Google Sheets. The categorisation was based mainly on the BARTOC²⁶ and the FAIRsharing²⁷ registries.

Metadata/Encoding Standard (52.4%): This category encompasses metadata, text encoding, bibliographic, and archival standards. Standards that prevail in this category are TEI (20.9%) and Dublin Core (17.8%), which are also the second and third most frequently mentioned

²⁴ Researchers' Survey - Question 4.2.1: How familiar are you with standards, controlled vocabularies, and thesauri? (e.g. TEI, Dublin Core, CIDOC CRM, Getty AAT, Getty TGN, SKOS)?

²⁵ Researchers' Survey - Question 4.2.2: Which standards, controlled vocabularies, and thesauri do you usually apply in your research?

²⁶ <https://bartoc.org>

²⁷ <https://fairsharing.org>

standards, respectively, out of the total number of responses. Few researchers use MARC 21 (2.2%), while only two researchers (0.9%) indicated they applied CMDI, EAD, EpiDoc, ISAD(G), MARC and Records in Contexts (RiC).

Ontology / Data Model (28.9%): More than one quarter of the respondents apply ontologies and data models in their research. The most popular is the CIDOC-CRM (11.6%), which is also the fourth most frequent answer among the total number of responses. This group includes a few researchers who use SKOS (3.6%), RDF (2.2%), Nomisma.org (1.3%) and OWL (0.9%).

N/A (24.9%): This group encompasses empty cells and special characters, or responses such as 'All', 'No use', 'None', 'Depends on the specifics of each project', and 'Varies significantly across projects'.

Name Authority List / Subject Heading Scheme (19.6%): GeoNames (4.9%) and Wikidata (4.0%) are the sixth and eighth most frequently mentioned standards out of the total number of responses. In the category Thesaurus (18.7%), Getty's AAT (7.1%) stood out, ranking as the fifth most frequently used standard among the total number of respondents.

The Repository / Service (14.2%) category refers to databases and services that provide multiple lists, gazetteers, thesauri and other controlled vocabularies. In our classification, explicitly named individual standards were categorised by their specific type, even if part of a broader repository/service. For instance, Getty vocabularies (4.0%) is the most popular service in this group and the seventh most frequent answer out of the total number of responses. AAT and TGN are part of Getty vocabularies, but they were grouped in the 'Thesaurus' category, because respondents mentioned specifically these thesauri, while responses such as 'Getty' were mapped accordingly to the Repository / Service category.

Other (11.1%): This group encompasses annotation, citation, character encoding and data retrieval standards, Custom (2.7%) and Project-specific (0.9%) controlled vocabularies, text corpora such as EGC, FrameNet (Latvian), PHI Latin Texts (0.4% each), as well as the WSJP PAN dictionary (0.4%).

Classification Schema / Taxonomy (8.0%): This category comprises taxonomies such as TaDiRAH (1.8%), Bloom's taxonomy, CRediT and EuroSciVoc (0.4% each) and classification schemas from various domains. **Controlled Vocabulary (4.9%):** This group is the most general and includes FISH vocabularies and SegmOnto (1.3% each), among others. You can see the responses divided into the 12 categories in the figure below:

4.2.2. Which standards, controlled vocabularies, and thesauri do you usually apply in your research?

Figure 14: Standards, controlled vocabularies and thesauri that the survey participants apply in their research

Coding/Programming

Out of 334 respondents, 170 responded either “somewhat familiar” or “familiar” to the question about their familiarity with coding or programming (4.5.1)²⁸. We then asked these 170 respondents which languages they were working with, offering three pre-filled answers (JavaScript, Python, and R) and an open field. Python (70%), R (38.2%), and JavaScript (28.8%) are the most commonly used languages, followed by Java (5.3%), XSLT (4.1%), Perl (3.5%), and PHP (3.5%). The remaining languages have a frequency rate of less than 3%.

²⁸ Researchers’ Survey - Question 4.5.1: What is your experience with coding or programming?

4.5.2. What programming language(s) do you work with?

170 respondents

Figure 15: Programming language(s) with which the survey participants work

3.2.5 Training Needs

One of the pedagogical principles of the ATRIUM Curriculum will be the learning-centred design, meaning that resources should be developed with the needs and experiences of learners in mind, providing clear objectives and outcomes. For this reason, a key part of the survey focused on understanding researchers' training needs, which training formats they consider more effective and which challenges they face when using online learning resources.

Perceived training needs

Question 5.2²⁹, about skills or knowledge researchers would like to gain through online learning resources, was an open-ended question aiming to collect some insights about the participants' training and upskilling needs. All responses were first cleaned, normalised and clustered in broader categories using OpenRefine.

Of the total of 334 survey respondents, 289 named specific skills they would like to gain using online learning resources, whereas 45 respondents did not mention any specific skills or training needs. The top 10 skill categories that participants would like to improve are visualised in figure 16: Data analysis (39.22%) and data visualisation (35.33%) emerge as the most frequently mentioned ones. Within the broader category of "data analysis", a few respondents

²⁹ Researchers' Survey - Question 5.2: What skills or knowledge would you like to gain through online learning resources? (e.g. Open Science, FAIR data principles, workflows, Automatic Text Recognition, data visualisation, data analysis, data publication, etc.)

noted specific data types, e.g., historical data, social science data, multimodal data (text & image), video data, as well as their interest in learning advanced data analysis techniques using programming languages. Here is an example of an answer given by a senior researcher in Humanities (12+ years working in the field):

“Data Visualisation – Advanced skills in data visualisation, particularly with platforms like Tableau, Power BI, and GIS software, would enable me to create more insightful and impactful visual representations of complex data. Data Analysis and Machine Learning – I’d like to deepen my knowledge in data analysis, especially in statistical analysis and machine learning techniques using Python or R, to apply advanced analytics in my research projects”

Other notable skills categories include (automatic) text recognition (23.05%), FAIR data principles (19.46%), data publication (18.26%), workflows (17.96%)³⁰ and Open Science (17.37%). These results demonstrate an increasing awareness of the importance of FAIR data, Open Science principles and proper data management in research practices. By improving these skills, researchers can enhance the visibility of their work in a responsible manner. Within the workflow category skills, it is worth highlighting that one participant expressed interest in learning how to develop training materials in a more systematic way. Such a workflow could be created in the SSH Open Marketplace based on existing best practices.

5.2. What skills or knowledge would you like to gain through online learning resources?

Figure 16: Top 10 Researchers' Training Needs

³⁰ Workflows are defined as a “sequence of steps that one can perform on research data during their lifecycle. Workflows can be achieved by using diverse tools, resources and methods, and useful resources are connected to each step.” (Barbot, L. et. al., 2024 <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.192>)

Programming & development (10.18%), AI & Machine Learning (5.69%), data management (4.19%), and text analysis & NLP (2.69%) appear less frequently, suggesting that while technical skills are relevant, they may not be the primary focus. The least frequently mentioned skills are in the categories of knowledge representation (2.40%), statistical analysis (2.10%), network analysis (1.80%) and data modelling (1.80%). In the "Other" category (3%), there are 17 answers that list skills and training needs not captured in the other categories, such as learning how to use digital humanities tools and new research methods, applying data-related skills in specific research activities, and improving English Academic writing skills.

These insights can help in designing training programmes and/or resources that align with the most commonly mentioned skills, while also catering to niche expertise areas, such as the knowledge and use of standards in data management.

Regarding effective formats of training materials (question 5.3),³¹ respondents could choose more than one option. While the most preferred formats were *video tutorials with exercises (self-paced)* (61.1%) and *written manuals, guidelines* (57.5%), the other two options also appealed to many researchers: *blended learning (combination of self-paced and live sessions)* was selected by 47.3% while *live interactive webinars, workshops* were marked by 43.1%. The curriculum can prioritise video tutorials and written guidelines, but can also consider the other formats. Only seven respondents used the "other" option, where possibilities such as Large Language Models (LLMs) and chatbots were mentioned.

At the end of the survey, participants could optionally provide additional insights about their online learning experiences and training needs that were not covered by other questions. In terms of training needs, no new information was mentioned, with a few participants reinforcing their answers from Section 5.2. However, there are some important suggestions related to training formats, namely:

- Training materials should include a clear description of learning objectives, the level of training, prerequisites, the type of assessment, the effort required to complete, and other relevant details.
- There should be training for different levels, not only for beginners.
- In written manuals, a concise abstract of each chapter would be helpful.
- Video tutorials should be concise, explaining a single point and providing concrete examples.
- Give access to the training materials after live workshops/webinars.

Another key principle of the ATRIUM Curriculum is active learning. The materials should encourage engagement by incorporating interactive elements, such as multiple-choice quizzes. As DARIAH-Campus allows for the creation of quizzes, the survey asked researchers

³¹ Researchers' Survey - Question 5.3: Which format(s) of training materials do you find more effective?

(question 5.4³²) if they found it useful to self-assess their knowledge as part of the learning content. More than half of the respondents (51.8%) said yes, while 31.1% were indifferent and 17.1% did not find quizzes useful.

Challenges

Question 5.5³³ was an open-ended question about the challenges they face when using online learning resources, providing insightful information. The responses were normalised and mapped into 27 categories of challenges, which were further grouped into nine groups, each one related to a broader theme, using Google Sheets. By categorising the various challenges in these broad themes, we can better understand the issues learners face and consider potential solutions, especially with regards to the Principles of Subject Selection³⁴ as defined in the guidelines for the ATRIUM Curriculum, in particular: *Relevance to the Target Audience, Foundational and Advanced Topics, Anchoring Tools in Digital Methods, Survey-Driven Content, Integration of Existing Resources, Cohesiveness and Progression, Flexibility and Modularity.*

Access and Availability (35.0%): This group of challenges primarily includes individuals who encounter general difficulties in finding resources (27.8%), such as those related to a specific topic or to match a particular goal. Moreover, some researchers replied that they have issues with the Level of proficiency / Level mismatch (3.9%), as they cannot easily locate resources that are appropriate for the learner's level of expertise (too advanced or too basic). This group also includes researchers who face challenges due to the overwhelming number of options (1.8%), making it difficult to choose the best ones or to know where to start.

The next group is Quality and Credibility (33.8%), encompassing respondents who primarily refer to the quality and credibility of resources (28.7%), which is the most frequent category of all challenges, and concerns the trustworthiness, accuracy, and reliability of resources. This group also includes researchers who point out issues with poor documentation and unclear content (2.7%). This occurs when resources fail to explain concepts in a clear and understandable manner, or when tutorials and articles are overly complex or poorly structured, making them difficult to follow or apply.

A significant number of researchers face challenges related to the theme of time management and scheduling (25.4%). Lack of time (11.7%) and stopping and restarting online courses / consistency (11.7%) are the most common challenges in this group. Furthermore, a considerable number of respondents refer to another theme: Certification and Recognition (14.7%). This group encompasses one category that stood out in the survey: lack of certification/recognition

³² Researchers' Survey - Question 5.4: Do you find quizzes useful to self-assess your knowledge as part of your learning content?

³³ Researchers' Survey - Question 5.5: What challenges do you face when using online learning resources? (e.g. difficulty finding resources, quality/credibility of resources, stopping and restarting online courses, lack of certification, etc.)

³⁴ Tasovac, T., & Garnett, V. (2024). The Guidelines for Producing the ATRIUM Curriculum. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13867113>

is the third most mentioned challenge, as many resources do not offer formal certification, reducing the perceived value of completing them, or people have concerns that online learning or certifications are not recognised by institutions, limiting their career benefits.

The group Engagement and Motivation (11.4%) includes researchers who face challenges such as a lack of interaction (4.5%), as some online resources do not offer opportunities for direct interaction or feedback from educators or peers, leading to feelings of isolation or lack of guidance. In Structure and Customisation (7.5%), researchers reported challenges due to the need for customisation (2.7%), desiring for more tailored learning experiences that address specific needs or learning styles, but also because of pacing issues (2.4%), lack of structure / no clear progression or roadmap (1.5%) and fragmentation of content (0.9%).

Another group is Price and Affordability (4.8%), which mainly includes researchers who face challenges due to the cost of resources (4.5%). Technical Issues (2.1%), includes categories with few answers, such as screen fatigue/difficulty reading on screen (1.5%). The group (N/A) (9.3%) includes researchers who did not provide information on specific challenges.

Figure 17: Challenges faced by researchers when using online learning resources

Other inputs

As explained earlier, respondents had the opportunity (in an optional open-ended question, 5.6) to provide additional information about their learning experience and training needs. Apart from what was already mentioned above regarding the training formats, and answers already

addressed in the analysis of training needs (5.2) and challenges (5.5), respondents also suggested improving learning resource reuse through train-the-trainer approaches, which will be taken into consideration in the recommendations for the ATRIUM Curriculum. There was also a recommendation to support exchanges between researchers working with born-digital and digitised materials, which could be addressed by another ATRIUM Initiative: the Transnational Access (TNA) scheme.³⁵ TNA organisers were informed about this specific suggestion.

3.3 Researchers' Survey - Cross Analysis

To gain a deeper understanding of the identified training needs and skills gaps, the next stage involved cross-analysis. By examining interconnections between the skills needed for the ATRIUM services and community groups, and also between the training needs mentioned by researchers and community groups, the goal was to obtain more detailed and targeted insights to inform curriculum recommendations. The data was cross-analysed with pivot tables using Google Sheets.

Skills Missing per Community Group

The skills gap among all groups is rather homogeneous. In all groups, the option showing no familiarity was the most frequent answer to the questions about coding and programming, container management platforms, and Web APIs. Only in the student groups (Master's and PhD) "Not familiar" was the most frequent answer regarding standards, controlled vocabularies and thesauri. They also responded with a higher rate, "Not familiar" to the question regarding ATR, but they might not need to perform ATR on a daily basis.

Thus, this cross-analysis reinforces the importance of creating training content on the above topics in the ATRIUM Curriculum, as detailed in the next section.

Training Needs per Community Group

All groups included data analysis, FAIR data principles, Open Science, text recognition, and data publication in their Top 10 upskilling needs. The small number of Master students (21) who answered question 5.2³⁶ indicated that they were most interested in using online training resources to learn how to publish research outputs and improve their data analysis skills.

Across all groups, the number of respondents who expressed the need to improve their AI and Machine Learning Skills is rather low. In view of the fast technological developments, the authors assumed that the need for upskilling in this area would be higher. Strikingly, while most groups indicated a high need in learning more about FAIR data principles, very few respondents in each group (less than 4) indicated they sought to improve their data management,

³⁵ <https://atrium-research.eu/travel-grants/>

³⁶ Researchers' Survey - Question 5.2: What skills or knowledge would you like to gain through online learning resources? (e.g. Open Science, FAIR data principles, workflows, Automatic Text Recognition, data visualisation, data analysis, data publication, etc.)

preservation and archiving skills. This may reveal a lack of knowledge in this area: for example, research data can be made FAIR only by preparing and managing it effectively throughout all stages of the research process and depositing it into a research data repository that supports the FAIR Principles. Compared to other groups, early-career researchers expressed the most interest in improving their programming and software development skills, which are essential for using ATRIUM services. Finally, the need to improve knowledge representation skills is low across all groups (fewer than four people).

Figure 18: Top 10 Training Needs per Community Group

4. Recommendations for the ATRIUM Curriculum

The following recommendations are based on the analysis of the results of both the Questionnaire for Service Providers and the Researchers' Survey. They serve as additional recommendations and, in some cases, as a reinforcement of what is already indicated in the FAIR-by-design methodology, developed in the Skills4EOSC project.³⁷ As explained in its guidelines, the ATRIUM Curriculum should adopt the 'FAIR-by-Design' approach to maximise its impact and efficiency.³⁸

One of the principles of this methodology is the reuse of existing training materials. The Questionnaire for Service Providers revealed that most services and software listed in the ATRIUM Catalogue are already well-documented and various types of self-directing learning content are available on their websites. Task 7.3 ("The ATRIUM Curriculum") will evaluate available learning resources and formats to determine which can be directly included in the curriculum and which require further development or adaptation. Additionally, while this report includes some suggestions, Task 7.3 will conduct broader research to identify other existing resources that align with the pedagogical narrative of the ATRIUM Curriculum.

Regarding other upskilling opportunities for researchers, a brief landscape analysis revealed that besides DARIAH-Campus, there are currently several other platforms and projects in Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, which provide open educational resources, namely:

- CLARIN Learning Hub³⁹
- H2IOSC project⁴⁰
- Programming Historian⁴¹
- Ranke.2⁴²
- Open Plato⁴³
- CESSDA Training Resources⁴⁴
- E-RIHS Academy⁴⁵
- Skills4EOSC project
- Galaxy Training⁴⁶
- SSH Open Marketplace

³⁷ <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/>

³⁸ Tasovac, T., & Garnett, V. (2024). The Guidelines for Producing the ATRIUM Curriculum. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13867113>

³⁹ <https://www.clarin.eu/content/learning-hub>

⁴⁰ <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>

⁴¹ <https://programminghistorian.org/>

⁴² <https://ranke2.uni.lu/>

⁴³ <https://openplato.eu/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.cessda.eu/Training>

⁴⁵ <https://www.e-rihs.eu/hs-academy/>

⁴⁶ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/>

- SSH Centre EU project⁴⁷
- ELIXIR Training Platform⁴⁸

While we are tailoring these recommendations for the ATRIUM Curriculum, which will be hosted on DARIAH-Campus, most of them can be adapted for use on other online training platforms. Given the length of the recommendations list, it may not be feasible to implement all of them within the scope of the ATRIUM Project. However, they can serve as a guide for future work and continuous improvement.

4.1 Training Platforms' Structure

Researchers described diverse challenges using open educational resources from current training discovery platforms in AHSS and beyond.⁴⁹ This subsection provides a few suggestions for the developers and maintainers of such platforms, primarily DARIAH-Campus, where the ATRIUM Curriculum will be hosted.

Implement Personalised Learning Paths

Although DARIAH-Campus provides a wide range of learning resources, it does not offer personalised guidance to help learners determine what they need to focus on. To help address the challenge of lack of customisation and, as one survey participant stated, a need for assistance in understanding "which tools and which knowledge" would be most beneficial to acquire through online resources. It may be worth exploring whether AI-driven personalised learning paths could be implemented in DARIAH-Campus to optimise engagement and motivation.

Show progression

The learning paths should break down complex topics into manageable modules, where learners' progression can be easily visualised. This directly addresses identified challenges such as "Lack of structure / No clear progression or roadmap" and "Fragmentation of content", providing learners with a clear sense of direction and achievement.

Implement robust filtering

The difficulty in finding resources was one of the most mentioned challenges in the survey. DARIAH-Campus has already implemented filtering options and this serves as a broader recommendation to all learning platforms. Filters should include at least the topic, proficiency level, resource type, and keywords to help learners search and find content of interest more easily.

⁴⁷ <https://sshcentre.eu/>

⁴⁸ <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

⁴⁹ SSH Open Marketplace, DARIAH-Campus, CLARIN Learning Hub etc.

Badging and Recognition System

DARIAH-Campus should implement a system of digital badges (e.g. Edubadge⁵⁰, Open Badges⁵¹) or informal recognition for completing modules or learning paths. While not a formal certification, this could provide a sense of accomplishment and micro-credentialing, partially addressing the "Lack of certification / recognition" challenge. Another option would be the European Digital Credentials for Learning (EDC)⁵², which are electronically sealed digital records (micro-credentials, certificates of participation) issued by a legally registered organisation for formal education and training, non-formal learning, online courses, and learning mobility experiences. EDC is based on a multilingual European standard, the European Learning Model, which integrates existing frameworks and vocabularies (e.g. European Qualifications Framework). This would also align with the European Competence Framework for Researchers (ResearchComp)⁵³, a skills assessment tool that researchers can use to assess their skills, whereas training providers can use it to adapt their offering to researchers.

Regular quality evaluation of resources / Feedback mechanism

Quality/Credibility of resources was another issue pointed out by a significant number of responders in the survey. In line with the FAIR-by-Design methodology, it is recommended that the ATRIUM project establish a system for regular quality assessments and updating the learning content as needed. In addition, a feedback mechanism should be implemented, allowing learners to provide insights on how to improve the training materials and/or the learning path. Regular quality checks and feedback mechanisms will help maintain the trustworthiness and accuracy of resources.

4.2 Training Formats

Based on the survey results, the following recommendations are provided regarding the training formats:

Use video tutorials with related exercises

It is recommended that the Curriculum include high-quality video tutorials and practical exercises to reinforce learning. The video tutorials should be concise, focusing on explaining a single concept or skill, and include concrete, real-world examples and applications. The exercises could be developed as quizzes, a tool already available on DARIAH-Campus.

In terms of accessibility, video tutorials should also be supported by highly accurate subtitles and a downloadable, screen-readable transcript to support not only people with auditory

⁵⁰ <https://edubadges.nl/>

⁵¹ <https://openbadges.org/>

⁵² <https://europass.europa.eu/de/what-europass-1/european-digital-credentials>

⁵³

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/jobs-research/researchcomp-european-competence-framework-researchers_en

impairments, but also those who struggle to follow instructions verbally, or those accessing the video without the possibility of listening to it.

Incorporate concise chapter abstracts in written manuals/guidelines

Comprehensive written manuals and guidelines should also be used as training materials, according to the survey. When developing these materials, especially in longer ones, it is recommended to include a brief abstract or summary (e.g. a bullet list of the key points) at the beginning of each chapter to help learners quickly understand the content and navigate the material effectively.

Implement blended learning options

To increase learner engagement and offer a wider variety of training formats, it is recommended to combine self-paced learning materials with live, interactive sessions (such as webinars or workshops), whenever possible. This is aimed at learners who value both flexibility and direct interaction with instructors and peers. Live sessions should be recorded and then made available, alongside related materials, to participants for review as well as to those who were unable to attend.

Create training for different proficiency levels

Explicitly provide training materials to achieve different levels of expertise: foundational, intermediate, and advanced. This meets the need for advanced training mentioned by respondents. The proficiency level should be clearly stated and easily visible in DARIAH-Campus.

Opt for shorter modules with clear learning outcomes

Create short, focused learning modules (10-15 minutes) that address specific skills or concepts. Each module should have clearly defined learning outcomes, a practice already present in DARIAH-Campus. It helps learners quickly grasp the content, addressing "Lack of time" and the need for more digestible content within the "Time Management and Scheduling" category of challenges.⁵⁴

4.3 Training Topics

Both the Questionnaire for Service Providers and the Researchers' Survey helped identify the skills and knowledge that researchers in the Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences need in order to engage with ATRIUM services, as well as the perceived skill gaps and training needs. As a result, Sections 4.3.1 and 4.3.2 present recommendations for potential training topics that should be included in the ATRIUM Curriculum, aiming to strengthen researchers' Open Science

⁵⁴ A good example of a modular course on DARIAH-Campus is Automatic Text Recognition Made Easy: <https://campus.dariah.eu/curricula/automatic-text-recognition-made-easy>. Opt for shorter modules with clear learning outcomes

and FAIR data-related competencies, as well as equipping them with the specific skills necessary for the effective use of ATRIUM services.

Additionally, Section 4.3.3 outlines the training needs reported by researchers that ideally should be addressed in the curriculum. Finally, the questionnaire responses from service providers revealed barriers to the wider adoption of their services, leading to a set of training recommendations tailored to providers themselves (4.3.4). Thus, the ATRIUM Curriculum can support both user upskilling and service enhancement, by improving accessibility and reducing the barriers identified.

4.3.1 Open Science and FAIR Training

Fundamentals of Open Science (OS) and FAIR Principles

Although a wealth of training is already available on Open Science (OS) and the FAIR Principles for researchers, including resources found on DARIAH-Campus and those developed through the Skills4EOSC project, the ATRIUM initiative aims to address existing knowledge gaps within its community. It is recommended to assess and repurpose the existing training materials on this topic.

Practical Application of FAIR Data Principles in Research

This learning content focuses on the "how-to" of applying FAIR Principles, targeting the large majority who are exploring or applying them to some extent, as indicated by the survey. Training materials should include hands-on exercises on assessing data for FAIRness, creating metadata using relevant standards, selecting a trustworthy research data repository for depositing data and other research outputs, and selecting appropriate licenses. Additionally, the course should include best practices in archiving and referencing software source code (using appropriate metadata for software), which, by extension, could be beneficial to SSH Open Marketplace use and metadata quality. Any training module on this topic should include demonstrations employing the research data repositories owned by some ATRIUM partners, as well as open science repositories, such as Zenodo.

Train-the-Trainer course on Open Science and FAIR Principles

To promote the reuse of learning resources and scale the dissemination of knowledge, the ATRIUM Curriculum should point to a training course designed specifically to equip trainers with the necessary skills and materials on Open Science and FAIR Principles, enabling them to deliver training within their own institutions or communities. This directly addresses the suggestion of train-the-trainer approaches that also emerged from the survey.

4.3.2 Upskilling for the use of the ATRIUM Services

As most services only require users to know how to navigate a website or browse through a graphical user interface (GUI), upskilling can be quite minimal. However, 15 services within ATRIUM require specific skills. For instance, some of the services are actually software development libraries (e.g. Annotorius, NEXUS, OpenLIME) and therefore require strong programming skills in the required language, usually Python, Java, or JavaScript.

ATR services (eScriptorium, OCR4all, Tesseract) are usually launched either via a container management platform, such as Docker or Kubernetes, or directly using a command-line interface. Therefore, it is strongly recommended that users know how to run an application via Docker and how to perform instructions in a command-line interface, as GUIs are not always available.

In addition, we recommend that the ATRIUM Curriculum include learning materials on the use of Git and GitHub and the identified programming languages (Python, R, Java, and JavaScript), as indicated by many of the services. Furthermore, the service providers are advised to make it clear to users (especially researchers) that they can perform their tasks directly on the application when a GUI is provided, and that strong computer and programming skills are only required for developers.

4.3.3 Training Needs as Perceived by Researchers

Based on the comprehensive analysis carried out in Section 3.2.5, it is recommended that the ATRIUM Curriculum contains learning resources targeting core data competencies, computational skills, and principles for responsible research (Open Science and FAIR), reflecting the most sought-after areas for improvement by researchers across all career stages. Topics such as research ethics, protection of researchers and data subjects should also be considered for the curriculum. Acknowledging that some researchers might be starting at a “baseline”, introductory learning content should be included in the curriculum covering basic concepts, research methods and tools in digital humanities, including a module on basic principles of computational and algorithmic thinking for those who aim to acquire more advanced AI-related skills. Potential training topics on core data and computational competences for arts, humanities and social sciences researchers should include the following topics elaborated on below:

- Data Collection, Preparation, Analysis and Visualisation
- Data Sharing
- Workflows
- Knowledge Representation.

Data Collection, Preparation, Analysis, and Visualisation

As humanities researchers frequently engage in data collection from traditional sources and require skills to process this data effectively for digital analysis, the ATRIUM Curriculum should include learning content on effective ethical data collection strategies, specifically from archives and repositories. Develop a comprehensive training pathway to help researchers improve their data analysis skills, ranging from foundational principles to learning how to apply Machine Learning techniques and AI to analyse text and large amounts of data, such as data acquired via a social science survey or oral history data. Ethics should be a transversal subject in this pathway.

Furthermore, data visualisation skills are highly desired and crucial for interpreting and presenting complex data. The learning content should cover fundamental principles and tools for data visualisation and demonstrate visualisation techniques in specific scenarios (e.g. RStudio, 3D visualisation, AI-trained data visualisation, using GIS⁵⁵ and Tableau for spatial data⁵⁶).

Specifically for archaeologists, as indicated by ARIADNE in the Questionnaire for the Service Providers, the curriculum should include a course on data processing and analysis using RStudio and collaborative research tools (e.g., JupyterHub). A good example of an existing course that shows archaeologists how to use, analyse, and visualise data in R is provided by Data Carpentry.⁵⁷

Furthermore, for researchers working with digitised images of texts, training topics on Automatic Text Recognition should be included to cover various facets of text recognition pipelines, including layout segmentation, text recognition model training, or on the specificities of working with printed or handwritten resources. For example, DARIAH-Campus already offers modular learning content on this topic, which could also be embedded in one of the ATRIUM Curriculum learning paths.

DARIAH-Campus currently contains an introductory course to “Artificial Intelligence and Prompt Engineering⁵⁸” that introduces scholars to Large Language Models (LLMs). The ATRIUM Curriculum should complement the existing training course with a more advanced course demonstrating how LLMs can be explicitly applied in research scenarios from the Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences. For example, researchers can be trained to use LLMs for analysis of large collections of texts (e.g. historical corpora) more efficiently and creatively, using key applications such as entity recognition, relationship extraction and sentiment analysis.

⁵⁵ On DARIAH-Campus, there is an introductory course to Geographical Text Analysis combining NLP, Corpus Linguistics and GIS techniques for humanities researchers. See

<https://campus.dariah.eu/resources/hosted/geographical-text-analysis>

⁵⁶ <https://campus.dariah.eu/resources/external/using-spatial-data-in-tableau>

⁵⁷ <https://alisonrclarke.github.io/R-archaeology-lesson/index.html>

⁵⁸ <https://campus.dariah.eu/resources/hosted/introduction-to-ai>

Data Sharing

A significant number of respondents expressed interest in learning how to effectively disseminate research outputs. Hence, the curriculum should provide clear guidance on the entire data publication lifecycle, covering general principles of responsible data sharing, and pointing to trustworthy repositories or data journals for publishing corpora, software, and libraries. Existing workflows from the SSH Open Marketplace, e.g. Archiving Textual Corpora⁵⁹, and the tutorial on Diamond Publication Models⁶⁰ recently published on DARIAH-Campus should be considered for the ATRIUM Curriculum.

Workflows

The Curriculum should integrate training on designing and implementing reproducible research workflows, teaching researchers how to connect smaller workflows and use existing processes and tools effectively. Such learning content should also address aspects of project management and collaborative research needs. The SSH Open Marketplace can be used to teach researchers how to create workflows for specific research scenarios. More specifically, for researchers working with speech and oral data, the CLARIN Transcription Portal⁶¹ can be used to teach and demonstrate a speech and oral data management workflow.

Knowledge Representation

Provide training on structuring and managing research data for discoverability and interoperability by providing hands-on training on the data modelling principles, showing how to design structured datasets, and demonstrating how ontologies and semantic web technologies can be used for advanced data structuring and linking. For example, the Vocabs Services⁶² can be used to teach researchers how to create, publish and maintain controlled vocabularies based on established standards and best practices in Social Sciences and Humanities, demonstrating how they can be used and highlighting their importance for the broader research community. More specifically, for archaeologists, a course on the use of Linked Open Data, vocabularies, standards and semantic web technologies should also help researchers understand how to use the ARIADNE portal.

4.3.4 Specific Training for the ATRIUM Service Providers

Accessibility Fundamentals for Digital Services (Focus on WCAG Basics)

This introductory learning content should offer to service providers an overview of web accessibility principles and the importance of inclusive design. It covers the foundational WCAG

⁵⁹ <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/gDzloY>

⁶⁰

<https://campus.dariah.eu/resources/hosted/gold-green-diamond-what-you-should-know-about-open-access-publishing-models>

⁶¹ <https://speechandtech.eu/transcription-portal>

⁶² <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/en/>

2.1 POUR principles (Perceivable, Operable, Understandable, Robust). Providers will learn about basic accessibility features, such as clear language, alternative text for images, keyboard navigation, and sufficient colour contrast. Service providers will also learn practical strategies to improve interface accessibility, focusing on readable text, clear structure, keyboard navigation, and basic ARIA use. The learning content should be developed with PRISMA's guidance, an ATRIUM partner that has experience in the topic.

Multilingual Access and Inclusive Documentation Practices

This educational content aims to overcome language barriers and enhance accessibility of applications and services for non-English-speaking audiences by using multilingual vocabularies (e.g. the ones provided by the Vocabs services), and translation services like LINDAT Machine Translation. Additionally, best practices for writing or contributing to multilingual documentation should be introduced, including examples from services that already have these resources. Several consortium partners have experience with creating multilingual resources and should be involved in the design of the learning content, e.g. CLARIN, ARIADNE, and OPERAS.

Minimising technical barriers: navigating institutional access

This learning content should help service providers address authentication across institutional barriers by providing a clear overview of systems like eduGAIN⁶³ and Shibboleth⁶⁴, and how institutional affiliations affect access. It presents strategies for managing access levels (public, academic, restricted). Practical examples and tips on supporting users through access requests would also be included. CLARIN could contribute to this learning content, as they have experience connecting multiple CLARIN Service Providers to several national Identity Federations and making password-protected resources (e.g., web applications) available to academic users from many EU countries.

⁶³ <https://edugain.org/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.shibboleth.net/>

5. Conclusion

This Skillset Assessment and Gap Analysis report presents meaningful results drawn from a twofold analysis of the Questionnaire for Service Providers and a subsequent Researchers' Survey. The insights gathered are critical for informing the development of the ATRIUM Curriculum, contributing to bridge the gap between state-of-the-art infrastructure services and the everyday needs of researchers in the Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences (AHSS). This work also helps support a broader understanding of skills present and absent in this community, service and tools usage, training needs and the challenges faced in using online training resources.

The Questionnaire for Service Providers identified the diverse skills necessary to effectively use the services and software listed in the ATRIUM Catalogue. While many services simply require familiarity with "Navigating the Service's Website/Application", a notable subset of 15 services requires more specialised proficiencies. These include, for instance, programming skills in languages such as Python, Java, or JavaScript for software development libraries, or the ability to use container management platforms like Docker or Kubernetes, as well as a command-line interface for Automatic Text Recognition (ATR) services. Furthermore, a significant number of services (22 for feedback, 21 for assistance) rely on GitHub for user interaction. This is the reason why specific questions about those skills were added to the Researchers' Survey.

The Researchers' Survey analysis revealed considerable gaps within the AHSS community, with a large proportion of respondents being "not familiar" with skills, such as using container management tools, Web APIs, coding or programming and command-line interfaces. This lack of familiarity was observed to be "rather homogeneous" across various community groups and reinforced the need for training content in these areas within the ATRIUM Curriculum. Specific recommendations were created to help fill this gap.

The questionnaire also identified diverse access barriers to using ATRIUM services, including technical requirements, policy-related constraints, outreach and language limitations, as resources are primarily available in English. Additionally, significant accessibility gaps were found, with the majority of services showing only partial compliance with accessibility guidelines, such as WCAG. For this reason, specific recommendations for training topics were included to address these barriers.

The Researchers' Survey provided insights into preferred training formats. The curriculum was thus advised to include video tutorials, incorporate concise chapter abstracts in written manuals/guidelines, and offer materials to attain different proficiency levels, meeting diverse learner needs. Critically, the survey exposed several challenges that researchers face when using online learning resources, primarily revolving around difficulties in finding relevant and appropriate resources, concerns about the quality and credibility of content, issues with time management and scheduling, and a lack of formal certification or recognition for completed

learning. These findings directly informed the recommendations related to the training platform's structure and training formats.

It is essential to note that, although the recommendations are tailored to DARIAH-Campus, where the ATRIUM Curriculum will be hosted, they can also be applied to other training platforms. Examples include recommendations to implement robust filtering to ease resource discovery, show clear progression within learning paths to combat fragmentation, consider a badging or recognition system to acknowledge learning, and establish regular quality evaluation and feedback mechanisms to ensure credibility.

The Researchers' Survey showed a significant perceived need for training in core data-related competencies, particularly in data analysis and data visualisation. There is also a strong interest in topics such as Automatic Text Recognition. Additionally, the survey reinforced that training in Open Science and FAIR data principles is still needed, despite the amount of resources on these topics already available online. While programming and AI/Machine Learning appeared less frequently as top needs overall, early-career researchers showed a particular interest in improving their programming and software development skills. These identified training needs directly informed a set of recommendations for the ATRIUM Curriculum, addressing the most sought-after areas for upskilling across all career stages.

The recommendations presented in this report represent a comprehensive list of potential improvements and training topics. Project partners in Task 7.3 will use the recommendations to develop the ATRIUM Curriculum following the Skills4EOSC FAIR-by-Design methodology, assessing which topics are feasible to include within the project's duration, given the available expertise and resources. DARIAH-Campus is capable of directing the users to external resources, facilitating the integration of diverse and pre-existing content. Finally, these recommendations will serve as a guiding reference for future work and continuous improvement, and can be adapted for use on other online training platforms, ensuring a lasting impact on fostering cross-disciplinary research through training and Open Science.

Beyond the ATRIUM Curriculum

The comprehensive results from this assessment are expected to be useful for the ATRIUM project in shaping its training programme and ensuring it is responsive to genuine community needs. In addition, it brings meaningful information about key topics such as the main research activities undertaken by respondents, with data analysis and data collection being the most common. It also sheds light on the types of data they primarily work with, revealing a strong focus on textual data, images, and tabular data.

The Researchers' Survey uncovered a diverse and extensive landscape of digital tools and services used for research activities in the Arts, Humanities, and Social Sciences. This diversity is notable, as a large majority of these tools was mentioned only once, indicating a highly diverse and fragmented use of tools where many niche or specialised solutions are employed by

individual researchers. This comprehensive understanding of tool usage provides insights to inform the strategic development of infrastructure services, tailored to support the diverse and evolving research practices.

The Researchers' Survey also provided data on the standards researchers actively use. It captured the application of numerous standards across multiple categories in researchers' work. Among these, Metadata/Encoding Standards (such as TEI and Dublin Core) and Ontology/Data Models (like CIDOC-CRM) emerged as particularly prevalent and frequently applied. This detailed understanding of researchers' engagement with a broad spectrum of standards is valuable to ensuring the interoperability of ATRIUM services with existing research workflows.

Beyond the immediate scope of the ATRIUM project, these findings hold significant value for the community at large. The detailed understanding of skills gaps, training needs and challenges across the AHSS landscape can serve as a reference for other research infrastructures, training providers, and educational initiatives striving to enhance digital competencies. The recommendations also extend to the ATRIUM service providers themselves, suggesting specific training to enhance their services. This dual focus – upskilling users and improving services – will contribute to a more inclusive and effective digital research ecosystem.

Annex A

Instrument - Questionnaire for Service Providers can be found through the following [link here](#).

Annex B

Instrument - Researchers' Survey can be found through the following [link here](#).

Consortium

Research Infrastructures

Beneficiaries

Affiliated Entities

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the ATRIUM project at the time of writing and may be subject to change. Neither the ATRIUM Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ATRIUM Consortium warrant that the information contained in this document is capable of use, nor that the use of such information is free from risk. Neither the ATRIUM Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ATRIUM Consortium accepts any liability for loss or damage suffered by any person using the information.

This document does not represent the opinion of the European Community, and the European Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of its content. Funded by the European Union. Grant Agreement number 101132163. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

© 2024 by the authors, the ATRIUM consortium. This work is licensed under a "CC BY 4.0" license.